

BIOECOLOGY OF TOMATO MOTH

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Abstract. *The given article presents the result of studying the bioecology of tomato moth development in the districts of the regions, methods and techniques for determining the timing of the appearance of the pest are presented. The timing of the appearance of the pest can be determined by issuing forecasts of indicators from the very beginning (weather, humidity, precipitation, soil temperature) and organizing control of it.*

Keywords: *tomatoes, temperature, humidity, moth, soil, insects, pests, pupa, protection, eggs, butterflies, bioecology.*

It is important to suggest that since vegetables are considered essential food products that improve human health, performance and prolong it, much attention is paid to their cultivation in our republic. Tomato is one of the main vegetable crops in Uzbekistan and occupies a special place in the cultivation of vegetable crops, since it is consumed directly.

It is known to everyone that in 2024, it is planned to sow 355.8 thousand hectares of vegetables (carrots, tomatoes, onions, cabbage and other crops), 209.4 thousand hectares of potatoes, 80.5 thousand hectares and 85.7 thousand hectares of sugar cane on the main areas of farms. Tomato moth, which is a quarantine pest of tomato crops, began to cause serious damage to the crop in greenhouses of our Republic in 2015 and in open ground (Tashkent, Navoi, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions) by 2016. (Obidzhanov D.A., Khodjaev Sh.T. 2014).

Besides that, the tomato moth (*Tuta absoluta*) damages the plant at all stages from the germination period to the end of the development period. The fact that it spends its life hidden in leaves, flowers and fruits makes it difficult to control this insect. Mature females live 10-15 days, males 6-7 days. Length is 5-7 mm, wingspan – 8-10 mm, coloring is brown or silvery, characteristic black spots on the forewings, filiform beak. Among the most important features used for its identification are the presence of antennae, silvery-gray scales on the forewings and characteristic black spots of the pest.

Definitely, the biological potential of this pest is very high, it lays up to 250-300 eggs and produces 10-12 generations in greenhouses during the year. The development of one generation lasts 29-32 days (Mamatov K.Sh., Bobobekov K. 2018). The tomato moth can fly well on its own, since it is very sensitive and mobile, it spreads over long distances even with the help of the wind.

Tomato moth butterfly

Additionally, the female lays eggs individually or in groups. Usually, 4-7 days after the egg is laid, the larva (worm) emerges from it. About 73% of tomato moth eggs are laid on leaves and 21% on the veins and stems of leaves. Apply 5% to leaves and 1% to fruits. The egg size is 0.35 mm, cylindrical, yellow.

Tomato moth eggs

Surprisingly, when hatched, the larvae are yellowish-yellow, 0.5 mm long. The head is black, at the age of 2-4 years it becomes light brown or yellow-green; Lives 4-15days (on average) and at this time turns 4 years old. The length of the adult larva is 8-9 mm, it is covered with silk. On the side of the shoulder of the larva on the first thoracic segment there is a semicircular black spot. By this feature it differs from the potato moth. Damaging the plant, it feeds on the inner side of the leaf and lives for two weeks, causing great damage.

Tomato moth larva

However, incubation takes place for 10 days in a silky cocoon in the soil or among plant debris, sometimes on infected and curled leaves. Fungi can also occur in the pores of leaves. The bulb is light brown, about 6 mm long.

Tomato moth bud

At present time, the tomato moth is one of the main pests of tomato crops, causing great harm to tomatoes, reducing yields by 40-50% and, in some cases, causing the plant to dry out.

Harm of tomato moth

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